

St. George's Cathedral

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Slavic Religions, Religious Place, Religious Complex

St. George's Cathedral in Ukraine has served as many things in the 20th century alone: the seat of the Metropolitan of the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church in the religiously diverse city of Habsburg Lemberg, the temporary headquarters of the Nazi-occupying regime in western Ukraine, and under the Soviets, a Russian Orthodox Church whose purpose was to promote Orthodoxy in a historically Catholic land. In the 1990s, it was the site of protests against the Soviet state, protests that called for this Church to once again serve the Greek Catholic Church and for Ukraine to not only have religious freedom, but also to be independent from the Soviet Union. A particular example of baroque Church architecture, the church in its current form was designed by the architect Bernard Meretyn (d. 1758) who combined elements of 18th century Habsburg architecture with his own interpretations of local Ukrainian churches. The Church architecture also reflects the hybrid nature of the Greek Catholic Church, with elements drawn from Latin-rite and Eastern-rite Christianity. St. George's Cathedral was built as a joint venture between the Metropolitan of the Church, Metropolitan Atanasii Sheptytsky, and Habsburg patrons. The Catholic Habsburg monarchy was invested in raising the status of the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church in the lands it had recently annexed from Poland. Raising the status of the Greek Catholic Church was thought to be an effective strategy to fight influence from imperial Russia and its Russian Orthodox Church as well as to create loyal Habsburg status out of Greek Catholics. This campaign of support for the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church resulted in a growth in Greek Catholic seminaries and the construction of new Church buildings, including St. George's. The Church's Baroque style was crafted with the assistance of prominent European architects and its artistic elements, particularly its sculptures of saints and Church Fathers, reflect the architectural style of the day. Situated on a hill, the Church remains an architectural symbol of the city of L'viv, today located in Ukraine and a testament to the city's character as a European city. Yet for powers that have occupied the city of L'viv throughout history, the symbolic importance of St. George's and its sacred nature have made it a target for forcible occupation. During the Nazi occupation of L'viv (1939-1944), Nazi authorities used Church buildings to create their occupying regime and coordinated religious ceremonies to create the (false) narrative that Nazi power had the Church's blessing. When western Ukraine was occupied by Soviet authorities, officially becoming part of Soviet Ukraine in 1945, St. George's Cathedral was forcibly transferred to the jurisdiction of the Soviet state-sponsored Russian Orthodox Church, a powerful symbol of the USSR's promotion of Russian Orthodoxy and suppression of the Greek Catholic Church in western Ukraine. Today, the Church is once again a Greek Catholic Church and while the seat of the Church is now in Kyiv, the powerful arch-eparchy of L'viv is represented by St. George's.

Date Range: 1700 CE - 2000 CE

Region: L'viv, Ukraine

Region tags: Eastern Europe, Ukraine

L'viv, Ukraine, a major city today in western Ukrain

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Ovsiihuk, Volodymyr. *Arkhitekturni pam'iatky L'vova*. Lviv: Kamen'iar, 1969

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

– Source 2: Zhuk, Ihor. "The Architecture of Lviv from the Thirteenth to the Twentieth Centuries." *Harvard Ukrainian Studies* 24 (2000): 95-130

– Source 3: Eds. V.S. Aleksandrovych and P.A. Rychkov. *Sobor Sviatoho Iura u Lvovi*. Kyiv: Tekhnika, 2008.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://lia.lvivcenter.org/en/objects/sv-yura-church/>

– Source 1 Description: Lviv Interactive: A digital encyclopedia on Ukraine produced by the Center for Urban History of East Central Europe

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.encyclopediaofukraine.com/display.asp?linkpath=pages%5CS%5CA%5CSaintGeorgesCathedral.htm>

– Source 2 Description: Internet Encyclopedia of Ukraine

– Source 3 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/865/>

– Source 3 Description: L'viv – the Ensemble of the Historic Centre [UNESCO]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Notes: Various excavations have been completed since the modern church complex was completed in the 18th century. These excavations were done as part of various restorations of the Church. These restorations took place during the Habsburg era (1905-1911), the era of the Second Polish Republic (1930s), during the Soviet period (1980 when the Church was under the jurisdiction of the Russian Orthodox Church), and in the post-Soviet era when the Church was located in independent Ukraine (1990s). See <https://lia.lvivcenter.org/en/objects/sv-yura-church/>

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1905-1911, 1933, 1980 and 1999-2001 [Source: <https://lia.lvivcenter.org/en/objects/sv-yura-church/>]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: A mixture of state-sponsored and church-sponsored initiatives

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Type of elevation

– Hill

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

- Clearing
- Trackway or road-surface
- Plantings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ A single structure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: St. George's Hill

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The Church complex has two design stages. The first was the building of the original St. George's church and monastery, which occurred sometime in the 14th century. What remained of this original complex was dismantled to build a new complex in the European Baroque style of the day in the mid-18th century. The buildings that stand today come from this mid-18th century project. The one exception is that the Church complex retains a bell from the original 14th century church. [Sources: Zhuk; Aleksandrovyh]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: St. George's Cathedral is part of a spiritual complex and monastery on St. George's Hill in L'viv. The complex itself consists of three separate administrative-residential constructions for the monastery and church administration and a bell tower. Source: <https://lia.lvivcenter.org/en/objects/sv-yura-monastery/>

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: The Cathedral has been restored multiple times throughout the 19th, 20th, and 21st centuries.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Notes: The cathedral was built over the course of 1744-1761 (by the architects B. Meretyn and K. Fesinger) and was restored in 1905-1911, 1933, 1980 and 1999-2001.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Notes: The first phase of the Church began in the 13th or 14th century, but little is known about this era of the Church

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God (The Holy Trinity)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: The origins of the original 13th-14th century St. George's monastery on whose grounds St. George's Cathedral was built are debated among historians. Some evidence exists that its origins can be found that the original monastery was commissioned and built by prince Lev Danylovysh in 1240, leader of the Halych principality where the Church was located. However, other historians argue that the original monastery has its origins in a later, 14th century period. The St. George's Cathedral and its complex that exists today was built on the initiative of the head of the Greek Catholic Church, Metropolitan Atanasii Sheptytskyi, with the support of the Habsburg Crown.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Notes: According to historian Ihor Zhuk, the initiative to build St. George's Cathedral came from Church Metropolitan Atanasii Sheptytskyi, but was financed by a specific group of church patrons who favored a western, more Latin orientation with the Church and thus proposed a Church in a western, baroque architectural style.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Notes: St. George's Cathedral is a single built structure. Yet the complex that it is included in features a bell tower as well as residential-administrative buildings associated with the spiritual complex.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Cathedral is the spiritual center of the complex.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Earth

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Sand

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Clay

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Wood

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Wrought-iron fence

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: The buildings are plastered brick and stone constructions with gable and mansard roofs.
The fence is wrought-iron.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: The outside of the cathedral features three significant sculptures: These three sculptures date from 1750 and are by the sculpture Johann George Pinsel. The first two are sculptures of the two "Fathers" of the Greek Catholic Church: Saints Athanasius and Leo. The third sculpture is of St. George the Dragon-slayer on horseback. [Source: Zhuk]

Reference: Zhuk, Ihor. "The Architecture of Lviv from the Thirteenth to the Twentieth Centuries". *Harvard Ukrainian Studies* 24, no. 1 (n.d.).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The inside includes a variety of decorative elements including icons, frescoes, an elaborate altar, iconostasis, and holy doors.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ is depicted in icons and frescoes inside the Cathedral

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The Virgin Mary and various saints are depicted in the sculptures of the Church and in the outdoor decorative elements

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Humans are depicted in frescoes and icons. In particular, the Church includes the portrait and crest of the Metropolitan who founded this Cathedral, Metropolitan Atanasii Sheptytsky.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Animals are depicted as part of the sculptures and in the frescoes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: Some decoration is non-figural.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: The pillars and walls are decorated with pilasters and ornamental moulding in the Rococo style

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Floral motifs

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The pillars and walls are decorated with pilasters and ornamental moulding in the Rococo style

Specific to this answer:
Region: Ukraine

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: Certain decorative elements are behind the iconostasis, which is hidden from view from the general public. In the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church, as in other Eastern Churches, an iconostasis (or icon screen) is present that allows certain rituals to be performed on the Church altar out of view from the congregation. One example of this is the preparation of the Eucharist

which is done behind the icon screen but then when completed is brought to the front of the altar, revealing it to the believers. Some Latinized Greek Catholic churches do not have an iconostasis or the doors associated with this structure, known as the "royal doors" but St. George's Cathedral has an iconostasis and royal doors at its altar.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: Statues of various saints, including St. George, St. Leo, St. Athanasius, and St. Onufry

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: See previous note

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: See previous notes. Statues are of saints and Church figures--humans but those with some supernatural elements (such as St. George the Dragon-slayer)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Statues are of saints

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Paintings include both frescoes and icons. The icons are the work of Y. Radiwilowski (1770-1771) and L. Dolinski (1778-1781). The murals date to 1876 (and the artist is E.-R. Fabiansi).

Reference: Zhuk, Ihor. "PL. SV. YURA, 5 – ST. YURIY (ST. GEORGE) CATHEDRAL", n.d..
<https://lia.lvivcenter.org/en/objects/sv-yura-church/>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: carved four-tier iconostasis

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Historians Aleksandrovych and Rychkov comment that the iconography reflects a mixture of western European artistic traditions with eastern-Rite symbols and distinct Ukrainian folk elements.

Reference: Aleksandrovych, V. S., and P. A. Rychkov, eds.. *Sobor Svīatoho Īura U L'vovi*. Edited by V. S. Aleksandrovych and P. A. Rychkov. Tekhnika, n.d..

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Portrayals of afterlife

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Iconography includes icons of the Virgin Mary and frescoes of religious figures and biblical scenes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Humans feature in the Church frescoes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Frescoes depict supernatural narratives such as Jesus's "cleansing of the temple."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Human narratives

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: One of the most famous icons in the Church is the Wonder-working Icon of the Virgin Mary, which dates from the 17th century. The icon is said to have offered divine protection against Ottoman attacks in the 17th century and was moved to St. George's Cathedral in the 18th century to bestow its powers on the Church. Source: https://risu.ua/bogorodichni-obrazi-z-terebovli_n65173

Notes: See later note about pilgrimages for more on this icon

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: The Church contains a crypt where Church leaders and political leaders are buried

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Christians believe that God can communicate with them through dreams, though these dreams do not need to occur in this Church or in a sacred place.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are material offerings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is it required:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Maintenance is performed by paid employees as well as clergy and parishioners. Historically, Greek Catholic priests did require parishioners to work Church lands but this practice ended in the mid 20th century.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Pilgrimages are present here, especially to see the Wonder-working Icon of the Virgin Mary, an icon present in the Church. The icon, known in Ukrainian as Ікона Матері Божої Теребовлянської [The Mother of God of Terebovia], was painted in the 17th century and observed to be crying,. More evidence that the icon was endowed with miracle-working powers was said to be found when the icon was said to have protected local inhabitants from an attack by Ottoman armies. The icon was brought to St. George's in the late 18th century shortly after the cathedral was built, endowing the new cathedral with a sacred relic. Pilgrimages in the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church are often centered around the Virgin Mary, especially icons of the Virgin Mary. Visiting certain Marian icons, or sites of reported Marian apparitions, is customary for some Ukrainian Greek Catholics who use these occasion to pray.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Notes: An important feast in the Eastern Christian tradition, including among Ukrainian Greek Catholics, is Easter, which is celebrated as a feast at St. George's Cathedral and other Greek Catholic churches. The feast aspect of Easter is taken literally. As is the custom among Ukrainian Greek Catholics, as well as other East European Christian communities, foods previously avoided during Great Lent now become a feast on the occasion of Easter as baskets are brought for a special Eastern blessing. They contain Easter breads, roasted lamb, decorated eggs, butter shaped in the form of a lamb--all covered with embroidered linen cloths reserved

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Feasting is connected to worship for the Feast of Easter, marking the Resurrection of Christ

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– No

Notes: Food is brought and prepared by believers themselves

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Festivals following the Eastern Christian calendar are celebrated and commemorate here

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: No statistics can be found

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

- Elites
- Non-elites
- Religious professionals

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

- No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Do large-scale rituals take place:

- Yes

Notes: Large-scale rituals that occur at this place include Holy Communion and all other Greek Catholic rites

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Do small-scale rituals take place:

- Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Reliable statistics are not available

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Daily

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: Synchronic practices include prayer and Holy Communion

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Wine is used during Holy Communion but not for the purpose of intoxication

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Present full time

– Yes

Notes: St. George's Cathedral is part of a religious complex of buildings that sit atop St. George's Hill. These include residential and administrative buildings for clergy and church administrators.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Present part time

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: In the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church, priests and church hierarchs are exclusively men. Women can serve as religious specialists as nuns. Historically a convent for Greek Catholic nuns, Sacred Heart convent, existed on the grounds of St. George's Cathedral but the building was expropriated by the Soviets in 1939 and the convent shut down. Today, the historic convent building is part of L'viv polytechnic university.

Reference: Dubryk, Yuri. "Sviatoyurs'ka Hora: Kolys', Teper, V Pryideshn'omu [святоюрська Гора: Колись, Тепер, В Прийдешньому]", n.d.. <https://zbruc.eu/node/34666>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: Even though the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church to which St. George's belongs has "Ukrainian" in its name, religious specialists do not need to be ethnically Ukrainian to join the clergy that serves at St. George's. Historically, members of this Church have identified as both

Ukrainian and Polish, though by the mid-20th century most Greek Catholics in this region identified as Ukrainian. Still, there are no religious restrictions preventing non-Ukrainians or those outside the region from joining the clergy, yet it rarely occurs.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Notes: All members of the clergy can access each area of the Church. Still, the space of the altar behind the icon screen used for certain rituals is a space reserved (during the Liturgy) for clergy, and not permitted to be seen by laypeople.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Historically, both a monastery and convent stood in the complex that includes St. George's Cathedral, but today that is no longer the case.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: St. George's Cathedral is maintained by the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church's administration, but also receives funding from the Ukrainian state as a historic site.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The Church is the seat of the Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church administration

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: As the seat of the Church administration, this place does have control over Church land holdings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– Yes

Notes: The Ukrainian Greek Catholic Church has land holdings that it does lease out in certain circumstances.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Notes: During WWII this place served as the headquarters of various bodies of governance associated with the Nazi occupying authorities. Today it no longer serves these functions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Function for water management:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: As the seat of power for the Greek Catholic Church, charitable endeavors are organized by the Church administration.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ukraine

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Reference: Other [specify]: Paintings include both frescoes and icons. The icons are the work of Y. Radiwilowski (1770-1771) and L. Dolinski (1778-1781). The murals date to 1876 (and the artist is E.-R. Fabiansi)., Zhuk, Ihor. "PL. SV. YURA, 5 – ST. YURIY (ST. GEORGE) CATHEDRAL", n.d.. <https://lia.lvivcenter.org/en/objects/sv-yura-church/>.

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